

As can be seen from the table, electrolyte addition has no effect on dilute suspensions but markedly increases the relative viscosity for moderately concentrated suspensions. The increase in relative viscosity per unit increase in volume concentration also increases with increasing electrolyte concentration.

Discussion

In a three layer swelling type clay, such as bentonite, the faces bear a negative charge. The hydration or swelling of bentonite clays occurs through water imbibition between the basal planes of two adjacent clay plates^{4,5}. The edges of the clay plates bear a positive charge due to broken bonds⁶.

The disperse phase in clay sols have a constant surface charge. The surface-potential rapidly falls off as a function of the distance from the surface, more rapidly for high electrolyte concentrations compared to low electrolyte concentrations, hence flow growth is favoured at high electrolyte concentrations, with consequent increase in viscosity⁷. The concentration of the clay suspensions also has a role to play, since the agglomeration rate in more concentrated suspensions can be expected to be more rapid compared to the rate in relatively dilute suspensions. Hence electrolyte addition has more pronounced effect on the viscosity of more concentrated suspensions compared to that in relatively dilute suspensions.

These points have been justified in the light of experimental results as shown in Table 1.

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Kinetics of Reaction between Iodine and *p*-Halomercury Phenols in 1, 4-Dioxane and DMF

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In earlier papers^{1,2} we have reported the study of the kinetics of the reactions between iodine and *o*-halomercury phenols involving the cleavage of

C-Hg bond in various lower aliphatic alcohols, 1,4-dioxane and DMF. These reactions were shown to follow second order kinetics and electrophilic substitution mechanism where the attacking species is either solvated I_2 or solvated I^+ . In the present paper we are reporting the kinetics of the reactions of iodine with *p*-halomercury phenols. Since the para compounds are sparingly soluble in lower aliphatic alcohols, the kinetics study in the present case has been confined to 1, 4-dioxane and DMF only.

Materials and Methods :

p-Halomercury phenols (halo = Cl, Br, I) were prepared according to a method reported earlier³. Iodine (BDH) was purified by repeated sublimation; 1, 4 dioxane and NN dimethyl formamide (DMF) were purified by standard techniques⁴. For following the kinetics of the reactions requisite amounts of $10^{-5}M$ solutions of iodine and organomercurials in the organic solvent (1, 4-dioxane or DMF) were thermostated at desired temperatures (20° , 30° , $40^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$ for 1, 4-dioxane and 15° , 20° , $30^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$ for DMF). After thermal equilibrium was reached the solutions were mixed. Aliquots of reaction mixture were withdrawn at definite intervals of time and quickly transferred to dry test-tubes placed inside crushed ice in order to quench the reaction. Optical densities of such solutions were measured at 450 nm (at which iodine molecules absorb in these solvents) at room temperature. The concentration of iodine in the reaction mixture was calculated by using calibration curve of concentration *versus* optical density of iodine solutions in these solvents.

Results and Discussion

The total order of reaction of iodine with *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo- or *p*-iodomercury phenol was found to be two by the linear plot of $1/(a-x)$ *versus* time at equimolar concentrations of the reactants. The pseudo first order reaction with respect to each reactant could not be followed due to similar reasons stated earlier¹. Specific rate constants for these reactions at different temperatures were found out and kinetic parameters like energy and entropy of activation were calculated by standard methods. Specific rate constants (at only one temperature) and energy and entropy of activations along with the error limits calculated in the usual way are reported in Table 1.

That a free radical pathway is not involved in these reactions was established by the observation that the addition of a free radical inhibitor, hydroquinone did not slow down the rate of reaction in 1, 4 dioxane, a virtually non-polar solvent in which a free radical pathway is probable. Table 1 shows that the rates of these reactions are faster in DMF, a solvent with high dielectric constant than in 1, 4-dioxane, a solvent with very low dielectric constant thus indicating that an ionic mechanism is involved

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NOTES

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF *o*- AND *p*-OHC₆H₄HgX (X=Cl, Br, I) WITH IODINE

Compound	Solvent	k, l mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ 30°C	E _a k cal/mol	-ΔS*	
				30°C	40°C
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgCl	1,4 Dioxane	7.8 ± 0.3	19.20 ± 1.42	—	1.6 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgCl	" "	40.0 ± 2.0	15.47 ± 0.62	—	10.8 ± 1.7
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgBr	" "	11.0 ± 0.5	18.60 ± 1.14	—	2.8 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgBr	" "	46.0 ± 1.8	12.90 ± 0.83	—	19.2 ± 1.9
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgI	" "	21.0 ± 1.0	17.50 ± 1.65	—	5.2 ± 1.0
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgI	" "	55.0 ± 3.0	11.99 ± 0.58	—	21.6 ± 2.3
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgCl	DMF	520 ± 18	7.62 ± 0.48	31.4 ± 3.4	—
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgCl	" "	3060 ± 180	5.65 ± 0.35	34.2 ± 4.1	—
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgBr	" "	990 ± 30	6.30 ± 0.40	33.6 ± 4.1	—
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgBr	" "	3840 ± 200	5.20 ± 0.37	35.4 ± 3.8	—
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgI	" "	1270 ± 45	5.50 ± 0.32	36.6 ± 3.5	—
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ HgI	" "	4440 ± 320	4.52 ± 0.30	38.6 ± 4.2	—

in these reactions. This is further confirmed by the values of energy of activation which are much lower in DMF as compared to those in 1, 4-dioxane. The values of entropy of activation are accordingly more negative in DMF than in 1, 4-dioxane. In fact, the kinetics of these reactions is very much similar to that observed for *o*-halomercury phenols system² and hence a similar four centre or three centre mechanism may be operative here in which the attacking species is either solvated I₂ or solvated I⁺. Arguments for the postulation of the presence of I⁺ (and I₃⁻) in these organic solvents have been presented earlier¹ on the basis of the spectral evidence for the presence of I₃⁻ in alcohols⁵. The activated state may be represented by one of the following structures.

It is interesting to study the variation in the kinetic parameters of the reactions of iodine with *p*-halomercury phenols as compared to those of the reactions of iodine with *o*-halomercury phenols. Though the values for the latter reactions have been reported elsewhere² they are shown in Table 1 for comparison. It is observed that the rate is larger for the *p*-compounds as compared to *o*-compounds in any particular solvent and likewise the energy of activation is smaller for *p*-compounds as compared to

o-compounds. This observation supports the electrophilic mechanism since it is expected that the ionicity of C-Hg bond will be greater in *p*-compounds (as compared to *o*-compounds), making the electrophilic attack by iodine easier. Further, the presence of OH group in ortho position may also have some stereochemical influence on the formation of four atom ring in the activated state. Both these effects result in faster rate for the *p*-compounds.

During an ultraviolet spectral study of *o*- and *p*-halomercury phenols⁶ it was observed that the benzene bands had undergone a shift in these compounds on account of Hg-X group and the OH group in the *o*- and *p*-position in the benzene ring. Interestingly enough the shift in the case of *p*-compounds is larger than in the case of *o*-compounds indicating that the ionicity of the C-Hg bond in the former is more enhanced. This correlates the kinetic data with the spectral characteristics for the *o*- and *p*-halomercury phenols.

It is of interest to study the variation in the rates of reactions of iodine with *p*-halomercury phenols with the varying halogens in the latter. The results (Table 1) indicate that the rates have the following order, iodo > bromo > chloro. The situation is similar to that in the case of *o*-halomercury phenols². This order is not expected if the ionicity of C-Hg bond is to be considered as the determining factor. Because the electronegativities are in the order Cl > Br > I, one would have expected the cleavage of C-Hg bond with Hg as positive centre to be facilitated with chlorine rather than bromine or iodine, in other words the order should have been chloro > bromo > iodo. Possibly the delocalisation of electron pairs from the filled *p*-orbitals of halogen to empty *p* and *d* orbitals of Hg plays an important role. Such a delocalisation would decrease in the order I > Br > Cl and thus the positive charge on Hg and hence the negative charge on C attached to Hg would decrease in the order iodo > bromo > chloro-derivative. If this effect is supposed to be predominant, the observed order can be explained.

A similar observation has been made in spectral data of the *p*-halomercury phenols⁶. The shifts in the primary band of benzene and the molar extinction coefficients for these compounds decrease in the order iodo>bromo>chloro. This again is in opposite order to that expected on the basis of inductive effect of halogens.

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